

Health Informatics and Quality Improvement

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Proposal Paper |

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Proposal to Enhance Revenue Cycle Management (RCM) Within a Healthcare organization: Addressing DRG Denials Through Informatics and Quality Improvement

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1. INTRODUCTION

Many hospitals face financial strains that negatively impact the quality of care and patient safety.

Efficient revenue cycle management is crucial for the operational effectiveness of healthcare organizations, which involves proper clinical documentation, accurate coding, and validation to capture the right Diagnosis Groups (DRGs) for hospitalizations. ⁽¹⁾

Within the healthcare reimbursement landscape, Diagnosis Related Groups (DRGs) were introduced by the Prospective Payment System (PPS) to categorize hospital payments and quality management, incentivizing hospitals to deliver high-quality care. ⁽²⁾

DRG is a system used by hospitals to classify patients based on clinical characteristics and expected resource use. It includes principal diagnosis, secondary diagnoses, and procedure diagnoses. Major Complications or Comorbidities (MCC) can impact DRG, increasing reimbursement rates. The system helps determine the appropriate reimbursement amount for each case, ensuring fair compensation for the care provided. DRGs promote higher quality care standards, encourage treatment efficiency, and discourage over-treatment for higher reimbursement rates. ⁽³⁾

Despite the significant benefits of PPS and DRGs, healthcare institutions are grappling with a pressing DRG denial issue, resulting in substantial revenue loss. This, in turn, prevents organizations from

maximizing revenue to improve patient safety or optimize resource allocation for patient care improvement.

DRG denials in healthcare refer to the rejection of claims for reimbursement by health insurance companies. These denials can occur for various reasons, such as coding errors, insufficient clinical documentation, or discrepancies between diagnoses and procedures. When a diagnosis or procedure code is rejected, it affects the DRG, leading to a downgrade and financial loss for the hospital.

This project proposes a solution to this critical issue. We propose training staff and designing and implementing an informatics solution that will help reduce DRG denials and enhance revenue cycle management. This initiative aligns with the themes of Informatics and Quality Improvement within the Harvard SQIL(patient safety, quality improvement, informatics and leadership) framework.

Improved coding and documentation are not just about reducing errors and financial losses. They ensure that patients are correctly identified and that healthcare teams understand their conditions well. This, in turn, leads to a reduction in errors in treatment and communication, identifies high-risk patients for appropriate care, and helps in the early detection of complications, ultimately leading to safer patient outcomes

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The prevalence of frequent DRG denials at most healthcare institutions poses significant challenges to financial sustainability and patient care quality. We evaluated revenue loss at a one of the largest healthcare institutions in New York City, NYC Health + Hospitals. Current data reveals that DRG denial rates surpass industry norms, resulting in substantial annual revenue losses totaling millions of dollars. In 2023, across all 11 acute care hospitals under the NYC H+H umbrella, over 3,000 claims were denied, representing approximately 10% of all submitted claims and translating to a revenue loss exceeding \$30 million. Despite this, the overturn rate for DRG appeals remains below 10%, as per corporation data in 2023.

documentation, coding guidelines, and regulations to prevent claim denials. ⁽⁵⁾⁽⁶⁾

Regular training for clinical and revenue cycle management staff, such as coders, clinical validators, clinical documentation specialists, and billing specialists, is essential to ensure accurate coding and documentation practices. Additionally, designing and implementing an AI-driven informatics system for regular audits of top diagnoses and procedures can help identify areas for improvement and reduce the risk of errors in coding and billing, ultimately leading to increased revenue and improved compliance with regulatory requirements.

The scope of the problem is clearly defined, and targeted training and technology solutions can

Fig1: DRG Denials at NYC H+H (2023)

effectively address the challenges faced in clinical and revenue cycle management(RCM). By continuously monitoring and analyzing data, NYC H+H can proactively identify opportunities for improvement and enhance overall operational efficiency.

3. LEARNING COMMUNITY

The success of this project relies on the collaboration and expertise of

key stakeholders from various departments within a healthcare institution.

- Project Leader: Director of RCM
- Project team: Representatives from RCM (VP of RCM, coder manager, Lead clinical documentation specialist, validator manager), Chief Finance Officer, Director of Finance, CMIO.

Poor clinical documentation and coding discrepancies remain the most common reasons for DRG denials, highlighting the need for ongoing education and training for healthcare providers. Additionally, implementing a robust denial management system and conducting regular audits before submitting claims can help identify and address issues proactively to improve revenue cycle performance.

The Center for Medicaid and Medicare (CMS) has programs such as the Recovery Audit Contractor (RAC) program, designed to downgrade DRG when there is insufficient evidence with medical records supporting diagnosis codes submitted. ⁽⁴⁾

With the rise of technology, most health insurance companies have been equipped with automated AI systems that can flag potential coding errors or discrepancies, making it crucial for healthcare organizations to stay updated on clinical

4. AIMS

The aim is to reduce DRG denials by at least 50% within the first 12 months following the implementation of the informatics tool and regular staff training on the top diagnoses and procedures. Based on the outcomes from the initial implementation phase, the goal will be increased to reducing DRG denials by 75% within the next 24 months.

5. PROPOSED INTERVENTIONS

Our proposed interventions followed the Learning Health System framework.

a. Formation of Learning Community:

- The process began with establishing a multidisciplinary learning community comprising stakeholders from various departments, including RCM, finance, IT, clinical operations, and compliance.
- This community collaborated through meetings and discussions to understand the current workflow, identify the root causes of DRG denials, and map out all potential causes of DRG denials on a fishbone diagram.
- A fishbone diagram was designed. (See Figure 2).
- Timeline: 1 month

b. Performance to Data(P2D):

- Performance data related to DRG denial rates, trends in revenue loss, coding accuracy, and clinical documentation quality are collected and analyzed to understand the current state of revenue cycle management.
- The data collected during the analysis phase informs the design and development of the AI-powered informatics platform and the development of strategies for staff training on current guidelines for appropriate clinical documentation and coding.
- Timeline: 2 months

c. Data to Knowledge (D2K):

- Data collected from performance assessments is analyzed to identify DRG denials' patterns, trends, and root causes.
- Insights derived from data analysis are translated into actionable knowledge, informing the design and development of targeted solutions. Staff training will focus on the top 10 diagnoses and procedures that get denied more often. The AI-powered informatics platform will be tailored to specific areas of improvement identified through data analysis, allowing for more efficient and effective decision-making.
- Timeline: 2 months

d. Knowledge to Performance(K2P):

- Based on the knowledge gained from data analysis, staff education and training programs will be initiated to promote best practices for accurate coding and documentation. Clinicians will receive ongoing training on proper clinical documentation. Medical coders, CDI specialists, and validators will receive ongoing training to keep up with standard industry guidelines and regulations, ultimately reducing the likelihood of claim denials. This comprehensive approach ensures that all stakeholders have the necessary skills and knowledge to optimize coding accuracy and compliance, leading to improved reimbursement rates and overall financial performance for the organization.
- The AI-powered informatics platform will be designed, developed, and implemented to address coding discrepancies and documentation deficiencies. It leverages machine learning algorithms to streamline the coding process and improve accuracy, assisting clinicians at the point of care.
- Regular audits will be conducted to monitor interventions' effectiveness and identify areas for improvement. Continuous feedback loops will be established to ensure ongoing education and training for staff members, facilitate the immediate correction of errors, and optimize reimbursement processes.
- Pilot programs will be systematically tested and implemented to minimize disruptions and ensure smooth integration into daily operations.
- Regular communication updates will be provided to all stakeholders throughout the implementation process to keep them informed and engaged.
- Timeline: 3 months

Figure 2: current workflow showing where there is an issue

Click on this link to view it online:

https://www.canva.com/design/DAF8o6mRWLY/VypfhFnSFixK5srwn1zOtw/edit?utm_content=DAF8o6mRWLY&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=ink2&utm_source=sharebutton

6. MEASUREMENT

To measure the effectiveness of the interventions aimed at reducing DRG denials and enhancing revenue cycle management, we can track the following metrics:

Metrics	Description	Target Goal
DRG Denial Rate	% of denied claims, indicating effectiveness in reducing denials.	-50% within 12 months; -75% within 24 months
Overturn Rate for DRG Appeals	% of successfully appealed claims, reflecting success in addressing denials.	+20% within 12 months; +40% within 24 months
Clinical Documentation Improvement	Assessment of documentation quality, reflecting training impact.	+30% within 12 months; +50% within 24 months
Coding Accuracy Rate	% of accurately coded claims, indicating improvement in coding practices.	+20% within 12 months; +40% within 24 months
AI-driven Informatics System Utilization Rate	% of staff using the informatics platform, showing AI adoption.	80% within 12 months; 90% within 24 months
Top Diagnoses and Procedures Audit	Findings from audits identifying improvement areas and training impact.	-30% denials within 12 months; -50% within 24 months
Patient Safety Incidents	Number of safety-related incidents, showing impact on patient care quality.	-15% within 12 months; -30% within 24 months
Financial Outcomes	Metrics indicating financial impact of interventions.	+10% revenue within 12 months; +20% within 24 months

7. CHALLENGES

Implementing Evidence-Based Practice (EBP) within a multihospital healthcare system presents unique challenges due to the scale and complexity of operations across multiple facilities. Each hospital within the system may have its own unique culture, protocols, and workflows, requiring tailored approaches to EBP implementation (7).

Coordinating efforts and standardizing practices across all hospitals becomes paramount to ensure consistency and effectiveness in achieving improved outcomes.

Furthermore, integrating a new informatics tool such as a Clinical Decision Support System (CDSS) across multiple hospitals adds another layer of complexity. Beyond the technical challenges of improving the human-computer interface and disseminating best practices(8), ensuring seamless integration and

interoperability across diverse IT systems within each hospital presents a significant hurdle. The CDSS must be adaptable to accommodate variations in workflows and clinical practices across different hospital settings while maintaining consistency in decision-support capabilities.

The adoption of new systems within a healthcare organization usually faces resistance among healthcare professionals, hindering implementation despite their potential benefits. The literature review revealed six main categories of barriers during the implementation of the new health information system: Human, Professional, Technical, Organizational, Financial, and Legal/Regulatory. Among these, Human and Financial barriers emerged as the major obstacles to successful new systems. (9)

Anticipated barriers to success, such as time constraints, funding limitations, and IT system constraints,

can further complicate the implementation process. Proactive planning, resource allocation, leadership support, and stakeholder engagement are essential strategies to overcome these barriers. Collaboration and communication among stakeholders⁽¹⁰⁾, including hospital administrators, clinical staff, IT personnel, and external vendors, are critical to navigating these challenges effectively.

Another challenge the project may encounter is training effectiveness and resistance to change among staff members. Patience and fostering a culture of continuous learning can help address these issues.

8. SUSTAINABILITY

To ensure the sustainability of interventions, we need to ensure that this is not added work⁽¹¹⁾; the project will implement a multifaceted approach to foster a culture of continuous improvement and data-driven decision-making. This approach encompasses the following strategies:

- Ongoing Communication: Regular communication channels and feedback mechanisms will be established to facilitate dialogue among stakeholders, promoting transparency and collaboration.

- Continuous Measurement: Performance metrics will be continuously monitored and evaluated to track the effectiveness of interventions.

- Training and Development Initiatives: Comprehensive training programs and Continuous Medical Education (CME) will be developed to equip staff with the knowledge and skills required to remain up to date on best practices and emerging trends in revenue cycle management and patient care.

- Optimization of IT Systems to support the long-term sustainability of interventions by updating software, enhancing data security measures, and implementing interoperability standards to ensure seamless integration with existing systems.

- Regular audits and performance reviews will be conducted to ensure that the training programs meet their objectives and that staff effectively apply their new knowledge.

9. SCALABILITY

Lessons learned from the project, including effective stakeholder engagement, data-driven decision-making, and sustainable interventions, will be documented, and shared to facilitate scalability. These lessons can be

applied not only within NYC Health+ Hospitals but also across other healthcare organizations facing similar challenges. Scalability will be facilitated through knowledge sharing, process documentation, and disseminating replicable best practices to drive widespread improvements in revenue cycle management and patient care outcomes.

Additionally, scalability in the context of system performance is crucial, encompassing structural scalability, which allows for expansion without major architectural modifications, and load scalability, ensuring that the system can handle increased workloads without compromising performance.⁽¹²⁾

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